

Combating Child Labour in the Post-COVID Period: An Indian Perspective

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ABSTRACT

India, as a developing country, has always prioritised its children as they are the future backbone of the nation. For the protection of the inherited and internationally recognised human rights of children and to provide all the necessary conditions for a better life, India has institutionalised the constitutional and legal measures. Despite the efforts of international and national organisations and institutions, child labour has remained a major issue in developing countries like India. The International Labour Organisation, United Nations Children's Fund and various national organisations have been incessantly working to eliminate child labour from the world. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has worsened the situation of many children by making them orphans and even leaving them without biological guardians. The pandemic compelled many children to leave school and work in hazardous conditions. Due to the joblessness and even the non-eligibility of the children to do economic transactions after being parentless during the pandemic, many children had to leave their native places and schools and settle in new areas to become daily wage earners. Besides these, many parents had to send their siblings to do wage-earning jobs to meet the family expenses after losing their settled jobs due to the complete lockdown. As such, the COVID-19 pandemic abruptly changed the lives of many people, and most children of poor families have become the victims and live miserable lives as child labour.

Key Words: Child Labour, Child Protection, Child Rights, COVID-19, Coronavirus, Lockdown

INTRODUCTION

Children are the future of every nation-state. A nation's development is also defined by evaluating the status of the development of children. It is the responsibility of a state to provide all types of facilities so that the children can develop physically, socially, mentally, and emotionally. At the international level, the United Nations has been continuously working for the protection of child from exploitation through child labour. The UN has declared 2021 as the International Year for the Elimination of Child Labour and requested the nation states to accelerate progress towards the goal set by SDG Target 8.7 i.e. to end child labour in all its forms by 2025. According to UNICEF, child laborers can be found in a variety of industries: brick kilns, carpet weaving, garment making, domestic service, food and refreshment services (such as tea stalls), agriculture, fisheries and mining. Poverty, socioeconomic backwardness, educational resources, alcohol addiction, diseases, disability, the lure of cheap labour, family tradition, and discrimination between boys and girls are some causes of child labour in India (Lal, 2018). Children are also at risk of various other forms of exploitation, including sexual exploitation and the production of child pornography etc. Since child labourers are forced to work in sub-human and inhuman conditions, they have serious health and mental issues. Recognizing this serious fact, the framers of our constitution have been emphasizing on protection of children from any kind of exploitation and directing the government to initiate both statutory and statutory measures.

In contemporary times, poor economic conditions lack of basic amenities or other reasons like lockdown due to COVID-19, many children left their schools. The UDISE (2021-2022) shows that 12.6 per cent, 3 per cent, and 1.5 per cent of students dropped out from schools at secondary, upper primary and primary levels respectively. The report also reveals that the rate of dropout is higher for girls than the boys (<https://educationforallindia.com/dropout-rates-in-schools-in-india/> on 30th November 2024). In the post-lockdown period, many parents failed to arrange educational expenditures for their children due to poverty and joblessness. Due to financial insufficiency, many parents unwillingly send their children to work as a labour in an unhealthy environment. The Census Report 2011 stated that there are 10.1 million child labourers in India between the age group of 5-14 years. Had this been so India would not be able to resolve the issue of child labour by 2025 as promised to the world community by ratifying the Sustainable Development Goals of

the UN. It is in this context, that the study on the efforts of the Government of India for combatting child labour assumes importance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:-

The main objectives of this study are as follows: -

1. To understand the term child labour from different viewpoints.
2. To analyse various Constitutional and legal safeguards for the protection of children from child labour in India.
3. To study the measures initiated by the Government for the development of children in the post-COVID period.

METHODOLOGY:

For the present study, both historical and descriptive analytical methods have been used. The concept of “history from below” articulated by E.P. Thompson to understand the problems of the weaker and vulnerable sections of society will be helpful for understanding and describing the causes of child labour in India. Historical methods will also help to trace the laws passed by the parliament for the protection of children from exploitation and child labour.

Both primary and secondary sources are searched to study the objectives. The Constitution of India, laws passed by the parliament for the protection of children, and reports of the international and national institutions are considered as primary sources of data collection. Various books, journals, magazines, articles, and internet websites are also used as secondary sources of data.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY: -

Child labour is a threat to human development. Innocent children are employed by industries and individuals who put them to work under pathetic conditions. They are made to work for long hours in dangerous factory units and are sometimes made to carry loads even heavier than their body weight. Many people hire children as domestic helpers or commercial labour and physically torture them even for a simple mistake. The children who work as labourers always lead

a miserable life. It is important to rescue these children from abuse and exploitation. The constitution of India has made numerous provisions to protect them. Besides the legal measures, the government of India has launched several welfare programmes such as the child labour rescue programme, and opening of the child line centres etc. This study is a modest attempt to study the measures initiated by the Government of India for the protection of children from exploitation and eradication of the problem of child labour, and crimes against children including sexual harassment.

UNDERSTANDING THE TERM CHILD LABOUR

Simply any child out of school is a child labour. According to International Labour Organization (ILO), the term “child labour” is often defined the work that deprives children of their childhood, their potential and their dignity and is harmful to physical and mental development. It refers to work that is mentally, physically, socially or morally dangerous and harmful to children and depriving them of opportunity to attend school or requiring them to attempt to combine both school attendances with excessively long and heavy work”.

The Child Labour(prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986 defines child Child as “a person who has not completed his fourteenth year of age” (Section 2(ii)). “Any such person engaged for wages, whether in cash or kind, is a child worker” (Mallick, 2018).

“Child labour refers to work that children are too young to perform or that – by its nature or circumstances – can be hazardous. Unlike activities that help children develop (such as contributing to light housework or taking on a job during school holidays), child labour causes harm to a child’s health, safety or moral development” (UNICEF).

Child labour is recognized as a serious and enormously complex social problem in India. Children under age 14 are often forced to work for as many as 18 hours a day. They faced many problems such as malnutrition, impaired vision, and deformities from sitting long hours in cramped crowded workplaces; they became easy prey to deadly diseases like serious respiratory diseases, TB, and Cancer. They are often forced to lead solitary lives away from their families, deprived of meaningful education and training opportunities that could prepare them for a better future. Child labour not only leads to perpetual cycles of poverty for a family but depresses the economy also.

CONSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL PROVISIONS FOR PROTECTING CHILDREN FROM CHILD LABOUR IN INDIA: -

The Constitution of India has several provisions for the protection of children from exploitation and child labour. Besides describing the children's rights as fundamental rights, the constitution also directs the government to initiate programmes for the development of women and children of the state.

Article 15 (3)-The State is empowered to make special provisions relating to the child, and states that this act will not be a violation of the right to equality.

Article 21-No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty, except according to procedure established by law. The Supreme Court held that "life" includes being free from exploitation and living a dignified life.

Article 21A (Right to Education)- The State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of six to fourteen years, in such manner as the State may, by law, determine. Where children are allowed to work, in such an establishment, employers must make provisions for the education of child labour.

Article 23- Traffic in human beings and beggars and other similar forms of forced labour are prohibited and any contravention of this prohibition shall be an offence punishable per law.

Article 24 (Prohibition of Employment of Children in Factories, etc.)-No child below the age of 14 years shall be employed to work in any factory or mine or engaged in any other hazardous employment. The Supreme Court held that "hazardous employment" includes construction work, matchboxes, and fireworks therefore; no child below the age of 14 years can be employed. Positive steps should be taken for the welfare of such children as well as for improving the quality of their lives.

Article 39 (e)-The State shall direct its policy towards securing the health and strength of the tender age children are not abused and that citizens are not forced by economic necessity to enter avocations unsuited to their age or strength.

Article 39 (f)-The State shall, in particular, direct its policy towards securing that children are given opportunities and facilities to develop healthily and conditions of freedom and dignity; and that childhood and youth are protected against exploitation and moral and material abandonment.

Article 45-The State shall endeavour to provide early childhood care and education for all children up to the age of six years.

Article 51 A (e)-It shall be the duty of every citizen of India, who is a parent or guardian, to provide opportunities for education to their child or ward, between the ages of six and fourteen years.

Along with the constitutional provisions, the Indian Government has also been adopting several legal measures (Lal, 2018) to protect children from child labour. These are as follows-

The Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986:- The Act prohibits the employment of children below the age of 14 years in 16 occupations and 65 processes that are hazardous to the children's lives and health.

The Factories Act, 1948:- The Act prohibits the employment of children below the age of 14 years. Adolescents aged between 15 and 18 years can be employed in a factory only if they obtain a certificate of fitness from an authorised medical doctor. The Act also prescribes four and a half hours of work per day for children aged between 14 and 18 years and prohibits their working during night hours.

The Mines Act, 1952:- The Act prohibits the employment of children below 18 years of age in a mine. Further, it states that apprentices above 16 may be allowed to work under proper supervision in a mine.

The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) of Children Act,2000:- This Act was last amended in 2022 in conformity with the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and covers young persons below the age of 18 years. Section 26 of this Act dealing with the Exploitation of a Juvenile or Child employee, clears that whoever procures a juvenile or the child for any hazardous employment and keeps the juvenile in bondage and withholds his earnings or uses such earning

for his purposes shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years and shall also be liable for fine.

The Minimum Wages Act, 1948:- The Act prescribes minimum wages for all employees in all establishments or those working at home in certain sectors specified in the schedule of the Act. Central and State Governments can revise the minimum wages specified in the schedule.

The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009: The Act provides free and compulsory education to all children of 6 to 14 years. The Act again clears that 25 per cent of seats in every private school should be allocated for children from disadvantaged groups, including children.

Along with legislation, a series of committees and commissions have appointed by the Government of India. Some committees such as the Royal Commission on Child Labour, the Labour Investigation Committee, the National Commission on Labour, the Gurupadaswamy Committee, and the National Authority for the Elimination of Child Labour (NACEL), etc.

In September 2016, the government amended the child labour laws allowing children below 14 to work in family businesses and the entertainment industry (excluding circuses) to create “a balance between the need for education for a child and reality of the socio-economic condition and social fabric in the country.” The amendment also introduced a new definition of “adolescents”—children between 14 and 18 years of age—and barred them from working in any hazardous industry.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON CHILD:-

There are several governmental, non-governmental, international, regional, and local institutions, agencies, organisations and committees committed to the protection of child labour. All of them have been continuously engaged in the protection and rescue of child labour around the world. The outbreak of COVID-19 in the last part of 2019 in China quickly spread across the globe and created a fear psychosis among the people. Due to COVID-19, millions of people died and a huge number of people lost their means of livelihood. The lockdown caused by COVID-19 posed serious socio-economic, political and psychological impacts which also hampered the educational process that directly affected the students. In India, 1st lockdown was imposed in

March 2020 and lifted in June 2020. Later in April 2021, the 2nd lockdown was imposed. During the lockdown, people faced different problems, including joblessness, lack of money, scarcity of food insecurity etc.

Due to the closure of schools during the pandemic, teaching through online mode became a challenge for the nation. Hybrid teaching techniques require hybrid tools to facilitate education. The poor parents/ families could not provide an Android mobile with an internet connection for online education. Besides, parents could not provide two or more Android phones to siblings of different grades to attend the online classes arranged at the same time. Again, due to less income or joblessness during the pandemic, many parents forcefully sent their children to work instead of sending them to school. UNICEF (11 June 2020) declared that Temporary school closures affected more than 1 billion learners in over 130 countries. Even when classes restarted, some parents were not able to send their children to school, especially girls became more vulnerable to exploitation in agriculture and domestic work (ILO *et al.*,2020). The closure of 1.5 million schools due to the pandemic and lockdowns in India has impacted 247 million children enrolled in elementary and secondary schools (Gupta *et al.*,2021).

Daniel (2021) reveals that in India the impact of COVID-19 on migrant children revealed a two-fold increase in the number of children who accompanied their working parents to the brick-making industry after the first wave COVID-19 pandemic. During the first COVID-19 wave, the lockdown forced millions of migrant laborers to move back to their villages in India. In the time of the imposition of lockdown due to the spread of coronavirus in India, millions of migrant workers returned to their homes sometimes without money, food and security. Similarly, the children who had been trafficked from their villages to work in garment and jewelry factories, sweatshops and car workshops in urban centres such as Delhi and Jaipur were returned to their villages in Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Jharkhand (Petersen *et al.*, 2021). But the situation has worsened when their parents have to take expensive loans at high interest from unregulated moneylenders to meet their essential daily needs. In this way, poor families become more vulnerable.

After lifting of lockdown in June, 2020 slowly many of the factories were reopened but the problem of workers still unresolved because the factories looking for cheaper labourers and the impoverished families deep in debt, and their children not in school, were agreed to send their

children to work in garment factories, bangle-making sweatshops, farms, and restaurants (ibid). As such, many school-going children and working children, due to the economic crisis, were forced to leave their native place in search of wages and work in big cities to support their families financially. Therefore, it is observed that the COVID-19 pandemic has created a situation of crisis, where more children choose to become child labourers. COVID-19 not only takes the lives of people, but also many poor children lost their right to education and are forced to live in an exploitative and dominative workplace where they are denied proper wages and security. Despite having constitutional and legal provisions, the problems of child labour have become acute in India due to the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to UNICEF, more than 1.5 billion children dropped out of school due to the restrictions imposed by COVID-19.

POST COVID INITIATIVES OF THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA FOR PROTECTION OF CHILDREN FROM CHILD LABOUR:

To provide free and compulsory education to children below the, the Government of India has launched several plans and programmes.

1. **Scholarship for PM Cares:** The PM Cares scheme provides scholarships to children who have lost their parents, legal guardians or adoptive parents during COVID-19.
2. **Samagra Siksha Abhiyan:** The government of India has launched the Samagra Siksha Abhiyan to implement the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 and the National Education Policy 2020. This Abhiyan aims to work to reach the UN sustainable development goal 4.1, i.e. to ensure all boys and girls complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes by 2030.
3. **Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme (2015):** The government of India launched this scheme to save girls from disappearing in childhood, schools and society.
4. **Childline India Foundation:** It is the nodal agency of the Ministry of Women and Child Development, which looks after the issue of children for protection and emergency services. Any children seeking emergency assistance can dial 1098 at 24X7. And get assistance and rehabilitation.

CONCLUSION:

Considering Child labour as a complex problem, the root causes of child labour, such as poverty, unemployment, lack of social security schemes, illiteracy, and the attitude of society, need to be resolved. India has been enacting suitable legislation and policies to combat child labour. However, the proper implementation of the policies and the programmes depends on the goodwill and participation of the general masses. Awareness and a participatory civic culture can save the future generation of society and shape their character in the desired direction.

REFERENCES

1. Ambedkar, B. R. (2020). *The Constitution of India*, 1st edn. Wardha, Sudhir Prakashan.
2. Mallick, M.R. (2018). *Labour and Industrial Manual*, Delhi, Professional Book Publishers.
3. Malik, S. (2010). *Handbook of Labour and Industrial Law*, Lucknow, Eastern Book Company.
4. Lal, B. S.(May, 2019). Child Labour in India: Causes and Consequences', International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR),pp. 2199-2206. (Accessed at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333644690_Child_Labour_in_India_Causes_and_Consequences on 1st April, 2021)
5. Daniel, U. (2021). 'COVID-19 and the changing face of child labour', **Down to Earth**, 1st July,2021. (Accessed at <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/news/economy/covid-19-and-the-changing-face-of-child-labour-77730> On 29th July, 2021)
6. Petersen, H. E. and Chaurasia, M (2020). Covid-19 prompts 'enormous rise' in demand for cheap child labour in India, **THE GUARDIAN**, 13th October, 2020. (Accessed at <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/oct/13/covid-19-prompts-enormous-rise-in-demand-for-cheap-child-labour-in-india> on 1st September, 2021)
7. Kundu, P.(2020) 'COVID-19 Crisis Will Push Millions of Vulnerable Children Into Child Labour', **The WIRE**, 21st April, 2020. (Accessed at <https://thewire.in/rights/covid-19-crisis-will-push-millions-of-vulnerable-children-into-child-labour> on 11th May, 2021)
8. Constitutional Provisions | Ministry of Labour & Employment|Government of India (Accessed at <https://labour.gov.in/constitutional-provision> on 20th June, 2021)
9. Legislative Provisions | Ministry of Labour & Employment|Government of India (Accessed at <https://labour.gov.in/childlabour/legislative-provisions> on 20th June, 2021)
10. Gupta, A and Sarkar, S (10th June, 2021) 'Child labour rises to 160 million – first increase in two decades', Unicef for Every Child. (Accessed at <https://www.unicef.org/india/press-releases/child-labour-rises-160-million-first-increase-two-decades> on 20th August, 2021)
11. Wylie, H (11th JUNE, 2020) 'COVID-19 may push millions more children into child labour – ILO and UNICEF', Unicef for Every Child (Accessed at

- <https://www.unicef.org/press-releases/covid-19-may-push-millions-more-children-child-labour-ilo-and-unicef> on 15th July, 2021)
12. International Labour Organization (ILO) and UNICEF (June, 2020) COVID-19 and child labour, A time of crisis, a time to act, Unicef for Every Child (Accessed at <https://www.unicef.org/reports/covid-19-and-child-labour-2020> on August 29, 2021)
 13. UNICEF and ILO (June 9, 2021) 'Child Labour: Global estimates 2020, trends and the road forward' (accessed at https://data.unicef.org/resources/child-labour-2020-global-estimates-trends-and-the-road-forward/?gl=1*mwbqr8*_ga*MTU2NjAyMzcxNC4xNjg5MDAyNTIy*_ga_ZEPV2PX419*MTcwMzg3NTAzMi40LjEuMTcwMzg3NjM2Mi42MC4wLjA On 30th June, 2021)
 14. 2021 International Year for the Elimination of Child Labour (Accessed at <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/child-labour/int-year/lang--en/index.htm> on 5th August, 2021)